

The “Solar” Orb in Egyptian Hieroglyphics

Precision conscious Egypt depicts the prime solar orb as a brown dwarf (now a gas giant); comparisons of hieroglyph diameters with the Sun, Saturn and Jupiter

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March, 2019

ABSTRACT

Prior translations of Egyptian hieroglyphs have often made references to the Saturnian sun, however, they have been typically ignored and stated as being the sun. However, the stele of Ramesses has a clear reference to both the rings of Saturn and to the two solar orbs. In this paper, brief analysis of the diameter ratios demonstrated on the stele (multiple) reveals Egyptian accuracy in depicting the Saturnian oblate shape, as the sun itself is nearly perfectly spherical. Furthermore comparison of two of the oblate spheres on the stele demonstrates $< 1\%$ standard deviation with actual satellite measurements of the ratios of Saturn's and Jupiter's ratio of equatorial diameter to polar diameter. Furthermore stele analysis shows the depiction of the transfer of the Saturnian god's power to the son (Har), and is found as depicted in the stele as the typical Great Man plasmaglyph. The average ratio for three compared stele being 1.21 for Saturn, but the actual being ~ 1.11 , there is a very high probability that the ovoid Cosmic Egg being displayed is Saturnian, and not Jovian (and clearly not solar) as it is only a ratio of 1.06 according to satellite data.

Keywords: Ramesses stele - Saturn - Jupiter - Solar orb - diameter comparison

Egyptian Record

On the Ramesses stele (dating according to the mainstream of Egyptology to the 1200s BCE [or as old as 2,494 BCE]), it says the following,

*“The gracious god directed Ramesses, the lord of the upper, and of the lower world, the ‘sun’, the director of truth, approved of the ‘sun’, the lord of **diadems**¹, Ramesses, beloved of Amun², the giver of life, like the ‘sun’ forever, Har-Hat, the giver of life, of stability, and of power. A gift of incense and libations. Har³ - **of the two solar abodes**, of life, of stability, and of power, the giver of victory and of magnanimity; like the ‘sun’, continually.”⁴ (emphasis added, see Figure 1)*

Figure 1 - Stele of Ramesses left near the Sphinx, with selected highlights

X: 0.4852

Y: 0.393

Note measurements are slightly cropped on stele

¹ Clear indication that the first ‘sun’ is Saturn. This text indicates the transfer of power from the previous lord (Saturn/Osiris) to the son, (Jupiter/Horus). This puts doubts to the stele relating to the pharaoh Ramses, who was probably named after this event, but at the end of the Jovian rule in the sky. Rather, it would point to the era following the Great Flood or less likely, before it. However, the stele could also be a memorial of re-creation and an affirmation of holy authority of the nobility, hearkening back to the original transfer of power from father to son.

² Saturn

³ Probably an early rendition of Horus.

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rfd9pFEbZA0>

Please note the 3 highlighted selections of the tablet (although more are worthy of discussion).

In A is our primary depiction of the Cosmic Egg motif, our “solar” orb, which is definitely of different equatorial and polar diameters. The ratio of X to Y will be measured with a caliper so as to be within 5% accuracy. Comparisons with Figure 2 and 3 ratios will also be made in Table 1.

In B we see the Egyptian depiction of the Great Man/Giant Man/Running Man with a clearer depiction of the torus under the arm. More information about this Thunder God⁵ (here the representation of the “Power” mentioned in the script) can be found in the author’s previous works⁶ and in Talbott^{7 8 9} & Cardona¹⁰.

In C we see a reinforcement of the collinear alignment, as well as a clear depiction of two imperfect spheres, one of which is also slightly larger than the other. A comparison with actual Jupiter:Saturn diameters will be made in Table 2.

There are many other worthy motifs upon this stele, including a large number of confirmations of the importance of thunderhawks, which supports the Native American religious assertions. However, they are not the subject of this analysis. Readers should study the stele for more evidence.

Figure 2 - Stele of Pharaoh Ramesses II; credit: Wikipedia

X: 0.799

Y: 0.694

⁵ [21]

⁶ [15] & [4] & [6]

⁷ “The Saturn Myth”

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5AUA7XS0TvA>

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svfWvSHh4AY&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seg6r6C_dtqB

¹⁰ “God Star” (series of books)

Figure 3 - Stele of Chia (scribe of Ramesses II)

X: 0.861
Y: 0.692

Table 1: Comparisons of X/Y ratios of 3 stele

	<i>Ramesses Stele</i>	<i>Ramesses II</i>	<i>Chia Stele</i>	<i>Average</i>
X	0.4852	0.799	0.861	0.715
Y	0.393	0.694	0.692	0.593
X:Y	1.23	1.15	1.24	1.21
Stand_Dev	5.11%			

Jupiter, Saturn, and Solar Diameters

The sun (sol/Apollo) is notoriously spherical¹¹, despite gravitational models¹² which should depict it otherwise¹³. In Table 2, its measurements will be presented in km accuracy, for X:Y comparisons.

¹¹ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2012/aug/16/sun-perfect-sphere-nature>

¹² <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/208344/why-is-the-sun-almost-perfectly-spherical>

¹³ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/gallery/well-rounded-sun-stays-nearly-spherical-even-when-it-freaks-out/>

By contrast, Saturn¹⁴ and Jupiter¹⁵ are notoriously *un-spherical*, and are rather oblate or ovoid¹⁶. The X diameter is ~ 10% larger in Jupiter and 6% larger in Saturn than the Y diameter (pole to pole), which represents very well the effect of kinetic rotation and angular momentum of liquid metallic hydrogen or other fluids and gases. The difference being, primarily, that the sun appears to be composed of crystalline plasma (a form of condensed matter)¹⁷, and actively receiving charge from the Galactic Electric Circuit (GEC), whereas the Jovian and Saturnian brown dwarfs are continuously powering down¹⁸, now starved of GEC supply since being enveloped in the sun's powerful solar wind. However, the arrival of Apollo/Marduk/Set is not the discussion of this paper. For more interest in this stellar electric physics, see the work of W Thornhill¹⁹.

Discussions of the end of Saturn's time as a brown dwarf can be found in the author's previous works²⁰ or the Nahuatl legends of the Mayans²¹.

What is pertinent, rather, is the diameters in Table 2, and their comparison to Table 1 ratios.

Table 2: Solar, Jovian, and Saturnian Comparisons and Standard Deviations

	Sun (km)²²	Jupiter²³	Saturn²⁴	Ratio J:S
X	1,391,982.8	142,984	120,536	1.186234818
Y	1,391,972.8	133,709	108,728	1.229756824
X:Y	1.000007184	1.069367058	1.10860128	
C_X		0.259	0.2475	1.046464646
C_Y		0.245	0.224	1.09375
C X:Y		1.057142857	1.104910714	
Stand_dev		0.86%	0.26%	
Avg C & Real		1.063254958	1.106755997	
Stand_dev vs. Stele		10.38%	7.30%	

Please note C_X and C_Y are caliper measurements from Figure 1, and may have margins of error that cover 1-5% variation. Some error may be due to computer rendering and/or penciling copy error from the original.

The standard deviations from C and the reality of Jupiter and Saturn make it clear, however, that the stele in Figure 1 clearly depicts Egyptians had line of sight knowledge of the gas giants. Their precision-based culture, with its emphasis on machining and civil engineering, enabled them to measure the diameters and depict them accurately to within less than 1% deviation in either case.

¹⁴ <https://sos.noaa.gov/datasets/saturn/>

¹⁵ http://www.answers.com/Q/Why_are_Jupiter_and_saturn_not_spherical

¹⁶ <https://spaceplace.nasa.gov/planets-round/en/>

¹⁷ Or the "surface" is a plasma sheath and the real sun is underneath.

¹⁸ As evidenced by their climate change, the dying Red Spot, and the changing color of Saturn's poles

<https://www.space.com/34508-saturn-north-pole-hexagon-color-change.html>

¹⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

²⁰ [15]

²¹ <http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

²² <https://www.space.com/17001-how-big-is-the-sun-size-of-the-sun.html>

²³ <https://space-facts.com/jupiter-diameter/>

²⁴ <https://nineplanets.org/saturn.html>

The ratios of X:Y, and of the real measurements taken by satellite leave little doubt as to the identity of the subject in A of Figure 1, and that is Saturn. Therefore, the stele depicts the passage of the power of the God from the father (Saturn/Kronos/Ra/Osiris) to the son (Jupiter/Zeus/Amun/Horus-Har). Hence “approved of the lord of diadems” (Saturn’s rings), and this would then confirm the date of this stele is *most likely* antecedent to 2000 BCE, probably closer to 3500-4000 BCE. It also confirms the hypothesis that the ancients could see the gas giants at least at night.

Please note the final standard deviations are compared with the average from Table 1, and not specifically with the stele of Figure 1. As the planets likely wandered closer and further away, the Egyptians own measurements would probably change, or again the carving may be less precise. The further is more likely applicable as the machining techniques of the ancient Egyptians is well documented to be extraordinarily precise.²⁵

Conclusions

Many unexplained (ie, avoided to be explained) glyphs exist in Egypt, many of which were translated reliably by Budge, which have depicted the dual solar world. For the first time, however, independent research has confirmed using mainstream Egyptological translations and glyph depictions, that the Egyptians had line of sight direct observation of the full sizes of the two main gas giants. The author contends that the real life inscriptions probably indicate (when appropriate and direct, such as in Figure 1), the exact size as they would have been seen in the night sky. However, as of yet, this is not proven. However, direct scriptural evidence provides perfect “smoking gun” evidence for Egyptian astronomy to have made reliable, within 1-5%, measurements of the equatorial and polar diameters of both Jupiter and Saturn. The author invites readers and scholars to find other stele and repeat the measurements to find more reliable averages to what the Egyptians *thought* the measurements were, and to compare these with satellite measurements.

²⁵ “Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt,” by C. Dunn

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